

Embedded Knowledge and Networks: Complexity in Antitrust Collusion Mitigation

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1. Introduction

Ensuring fair and open markets has long been a critical mandate of competition authorities. Yet the growing complexity and digitalization of markets, which demand novel analytical tools capable of integrating large-scale, high-dimensional data to support enforcement decisions, pose new obstacles. This project is a direct response to this challenge. It stems from the necessity to develop a unifying analytical framework to aid in the regulatory tasks of supervising competitive markets in Portugal. Its main contribution will be the development of a Knowledge Graph that consolidates relational information about entities that participate in competitive markets. This decision-support tool would enable regulators to reason over cases of collusion based on similar decisions or to assess the potential impacts of mergers and acquisitions on competition, among other applications. But more importantly, identify missing information (links) or classify the risk of collusion of specific market segments. Further contributions include the creation of a dashboard offering stakeholders access to graph-based metrics and a case study on the use of knowledge representation learning to identify possible hidden links between entities and the main active market segments.

Established antitrust tools such as leniency programs, complaints-based investigations, or traditional market analysis have been critical, but are no longer sufficient in environments where economic agents operate with sophisticated concealment (Ysewyn & Kahmann, 2018). Rather, the underlying mechanics behind collusive and cartel behavior often make these unfeasible or too cumbersome as they require an understanding of the market organization beyond the formal ties between the participating entities. Although network analysis has been used, with limited scope, to aid in offering such mapping of the market organization, it is often difficult to combine other types of structured information with graph-based features as inputs to feed traditional AI/ML methods. However, recent advances in both Natural Language Processing (NLP) and structured knowledge representations in the form of knowledge graphs have made it possible to integrate data from both structured and unstructured sources into a unified data structure, which serves both as an entry point to represent latent knowledge structures and as input for ML models to perform inference.

In a broader sense, computational techniques have become more widespread in antitrust investigations (Amthauer et al., 2023). However, as algorithms and AI play a larger role in enforcement and decision-making systems, “explainability” has become a major concern (Linardatos et al., 2020). That is, the opacity of complex "black box" models, such as deep neural

networks, fundamentally challenges traditional legal principles of transparency and accountability (Schrepel & Groza, 2025). Graph-based network analysis offers a counterweight to the prevalence of “unexplainable” ML systems. Specifically, knowledge graphs have an established history of representing symbolic, i.e., explicit knowledge (Ji et al., 2022). They consist of two key elements: an ontology or schema and a reasoning engine that applies inference over semantic information represented in the graph (Ehrlinger & Wöß, 2016). A set of standards have been defined for knowledge graphs, such as RDF (Resource Description Framework) designed for cross-system understanding (Negro et al., 2023), as well as LPG (Labelled Property Graph), optimized for performance.

While past research has explored many architectures and algorithms to identify and assess antitrust violations computationally, network-based approaches still need to be explored, especially such systems that leverage semantic representations. The project thus pursues three distinct goals:

1. Develop a prototype Knowledge Graph summarizing and codifying the extant decision-making process governing market interventions, particularly emphasizing the relational information between entities relevant to the Stakeholder’s regulatory activities;
2. Explore an analytical case study showing the value of structured knowledge representations to the end of inferring missing relationships, such as “missing” competition linkages and market segmentation;
3. Design a plan of action incorporating the prototype in the stakeholder's current activities and possible pathways to integrate it with future ML and AI applications, e.g., conversational agents using the knowledge graph as a backend for factual grounding.

The project team combines experts in Network Analysis, Economics, Data Science, and Machine Learning. The team also possesses experience in developing consultancy projects with the World Bank and OECD. In the latter, the same core team developed a project with the OECD to explore the possible application of ML methods to support the activities of the Portuguese Audit Court (Tribunal de Contas). The project involved desk research and prototype phases, with the latter involving implementing ML models for the automated classification of 31 red flags, as agreed upon by the stakeholders. That project, in particular, showed the importance of having a mixed team with competencies in Data Science and Machine Learning and the domain of application, a recipe that we follow in this project with a mix of researchers from Data and Economic sciences.

The present report offers a first mapping of the knowledge base that underpins this project. It encompasses a comprehensive literature review focused on computational antitrust,

particularly emphasizing applications of network analysis within this domain. Additionally, the report catalogs existing data sources and identifies novel datasets that will be validated in collaboration with external stakeholders. Following a rigorous assessment of data quality, these sources will form the foundation for developing a robust, graph-based schema intended to support a versatile graph data store, enabling multi-purpose analyses fundamental to the project's objectives. Finally, a case study on link prediction, demonstrates the system's potential to significantly advance the capabilities of antitrust analysis.

2. Computational Antitrust - A Bibliometric Analysis

2.1. Computational Antitrust

Antitrust denotes the body of laws and regulations designed to safeguard market competition and prevent monopolistic or collusive practices that harm consumers and stifle innovation (Motta, 2004). Its jurisprudence has historically been marked by paradigm shifts: from an early focus on textual legal interpretation (Antitrust 1.0) to a later prioritization of economic efficiency considerations (Antitrust 2.0) (Posner, 2009; Schrepel, 2021). The emergent emphasis on “data-centered enforcement” represents the latest shift, prompted by the complexities introduced by digital markets (Schrepel & Groza, 2025). Formally referred to as “computational antitrust” (Antitrust 3.0), this interdisciplinary field is concerned with leveraging advanced analytical tools to enhance the detection and prevention of anti-competitive practices.

Scientific interest in computational antitrust has been increasing in recent years. More significantly, recent evidence suggests a convergence toward computational antitrust worldwide. In their latest report, Schrepel and Groza (2025), drawing on contributions from 25 antitrust agencies, identify key priorities including the deployment of AI-enabled tools to detect infringements, investment in data infrastructure to manage large-scale datasets, and institutional reforms aimed at embedding computational methods. Within this evolving framework, network analysis has emerged as a particularly robust technique for understanding the complex and interconnected nature of modern markets. To that end, this literature review integrates insights derived from an extensive bibliometric analysis of network-based approaches in antitrust. The objective is to synthesize the extant scholarly work, thereby establishing a rigorous foundation for assessing the current state of research and identifying promising avenues for future inquiry.

2.2. Materials and Methods

We began by performing a systematic keyword search through Web of Science, a leading scholarly database renowned for its extensive coverage of peer-reviewed literature

(Archambault et al., 2009). We first extracted and compiled all articles containing the term "antitrust" without imposing any publication date restrictions, thereby ensuring comprehensive coverage of both foundational and emerging works. Inclusion criteria required the use or explicit conceptual discussion of computational tools characterized by a set of pre-defined keywords, as shown in Figure 1. Given the scope of the project, as well as the opportunity to leverage network analysis for modelling the competitive landscape of the Portuguese public sector, the present bibliometric analysis focuses on the subset of articles employing network-based approaches.

This review is guided by the following research questions: *RQ1*. Landscape: Who are the key authors, institutions, and publications shaping this field of research? *RQ2*. Methodology: What research methods, conceptual frameworks, data sources, and application domains are most prevalent? *RQ3*. Trends: What are the dominant thematic trends and evolutionary patterns in the research? *RQ4*. Gaps: What specific gaps and opportunities exist, particularly concerning the use of network analysis?

2.3. Results

2.3.1. Stylized Facts

We present the distribution of the selected articles across the assigned hierarchical ontology in Figure 1. A total of 68 articles on computational antitrust were identified, of which a relatively small subset of 13 articles addresses network-based approaches. The latter includes articles that originate from 9 countries, with the United States contributing the most articles. With regards to the data type and sources, these range from antitrust cases spanning mining and consumer goods (e.g., from the Italian Antitrust Authority and European Commission, respectively) to health insurance and airlines data. A complete overview of the main contributions in the field is presented in Appendix A (Table 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of articles

Additionally, we visualize and trace the knowledge map of antitrust research using a keyword co-occurrence network, as illustrated in Figure 2. The relative importance of terms (node size) and the strength of the conceptual relationships (weight of links) reveal an extensive intellectual structure with dense thematic clusters (represented by 8 communities), as measured by keyword joint appearance. Most importantly, it shows that artificial intelligence, machine learning and network-based approaches are emerging research fronts.

Within the first body of literature, Bilotkach and Hüsichelrath (2019) examine the impact of alliance formations (i.e. joint ventures in the airline industry) on airlines' network configurations and productive efficiency given antitrust-immunity considerations. Czerny et al. (2021) adopt a similar line of inquiry by modeling airline collaborations under antitrust immunity. Both studies provide critical insights into the trade-off between efficiency gains that result from cooperation and the potential for reduced market competition under antitrust-immune joint ventures.

Early theoretical contributions provided a crucial bridge between network analysis and antitrust enforcement. Economides and White (1994), for instance, systematically linked network properties like compatibility to established economic concepts of complementarity and vertical integration, offering a coherent framework for analyzing the competitive implications of mergers, joint ventures, and vertical restraints. Subsequent empirical work by Grau-Carles and Cuerdo-Mir (2016) employed network analysis to dissect a cartel, successfully identifying centrally important firms and structural vulnerabilities based on network topology. Their findings have profound implications for leniency regimes, suggesting that their effectiveness depends not just on when a firm reports, but on the structural role of the reporting member within the cartel's network.

Studies by Enriques and Romano (2019) and by extension, Romano (2021), expand the network framework to understand institutional shareholder behavior. Specifically, building upon a rich body of empirical studies, Romano (2021) advocates for "Network Sensitive Regulation" (NSR), arguing that "[NSR] grounded in network theory would allow policymakers to account for the interconnections among markets and among institutional investors and their portfolio firms" (p. 370). That is, unlike traditional "atomistic" regulations that focus narrowly on individual firms or institutions in isolation, NSR considers how these entities are embedded within broader networks and how their actions and ownership structures can affect systemic risks and competitive dynamics across interconnected markets. Within the healthcare labor market, Westra et al. (2016) investigate specialist physician networks to assess how specialist sharing shapes competitive interactions and resource distribution. The study shows how professional networks and institutional ties can shape market structures beyond formal ownership patterns, complicating standard antitrust evaluations.

2.3.3. Main Themes

A common thread across the selected studies is the move from market as a loose aggregation of actors to market as a dynamically evolving network of interactions. As such, main themes identified in the literature concern how network topology or attributes shape antitrust outcome

(Bimpikis et al., 2019; Economides & White, 1994; Elliott & Galeotti, 2019; Grau-Carles & Cuerdo-Mir, 2016) and how contextual (e.g., the presence of an antitrust authority, healthcare regulations, airline route constraints) or sectoral specificities inform network dynamics (Bilotkach & Hüscherlath, 2019; Czerny et al., 2021; Enriques & Romano, 2019; Roldán, 2012; Romano, 2021; Westra et al. 2016), underscoring the need for tailored network models sensitive to industry-specific mechanisms.

2.3.4. Network-based Methodologies

The results show that while the use of econometrics and statistical methods are common, dominant network-based methodologies offering more systemic insights include Bayesian networks and techniques derived from graph theory. The former provides a probabilistic framework to represent dependencies and causal relationships among market players and their behaviors, useful for understanding uncertainties and interactions in competitive dynamics. For instance, Mortera et al., (2016) propose Bayesian networks as decision support for antitrust enforcement, integrating probabilistic reasoning over relational structures to handle data uncertainties and infer hidden collusive links. This approach facilitates the incorporation of latent network structures and incomplete data into diagnostics, aiding agencies in assessing cartel risks and merger effects from complex datasets. Whereas graph theory, as exemplified by Roldán (2012) and Bimpikis et al. (2019), offers mathematical tools to analyze the topology, connectivity, paths, and centrality in networks, relevant to understanding market power, barriers to entry, and spillovers across linked markets. Specifically, Bimpikis et al. (2019) advance oligopoly theory by incorporating explicit market network structures into Cournot competition models. This bipartite network perspective deviates from classical homogenous market assumptions, revealing how network topology governs equilibria, influences firm profits, and consumer surplus.

More recently, calls for reframing antitrust analysis through the lens of “complexity science” foreground key features such as multilevel interactions, feedback loops, and adaptive behavior (Petit & Schrepel, 2024). These offer promising extensions and open new avenues for both research and enforcement, advocating for methods and policies that address markets characterized by evolution, uncertainty, and nonlinearity.

2.4. Conclusion

The present literature review synthesizes a cross-section of leading studies that have advanced both the theory and empirics of network-based antitrust analysis. It covers foundational models of market structure (e.g., Cournot in networks), empirical detection of collusion, sector-specific applications in healthcare and airlines, and complexity science perspectives. These findings

underscore the novelty of the project, which is among the first to apply network analysis within the realm of public administration. They reveal that network-based approaches offer richer diagnostic and predictive capabilities for antitrust analysis by capturing competitive dynamics beyond traditional market definitions. Key research frontiers include advancing semantic network modeling, incorporating dynamic and multilayer network structures, and integrating explainable AI into regulatory frameworks to translate these methodological advances into practice. However, fully realizing the potential of network-based approaches in antitrust enforcement requires bridging methodological gaps, improving interdisciplinary communication, and achieving institutional integration.

3. Building Market Observability - From Data to Dashboard

3.1. Data Architecture Proposal

Figure 3 illustrates the platform architecture, which facilitates the lifecycle of public procurement data from ingestion to visualization. The process begins by scraping diverse public sources regarding contracts, entities, and individuals. This data is ingested into CouchDB following a medallion architecture pattern: raw data is stored as Bronze, normalized and cleaned data as Silver, and fully aggregated records as Gold. To ensure data integrity, the Gold-level data undergoes semantic validation using a schema defined in LinkML. Once validated, the data is loaded into Neo4j to establish an operational property graph for data science tasks and visualization.

The technology stack is selected to balance flexible ingestion with strict structural validation. CouchDB is utilized for the storage layer because its document-oriented structure efficiently handles the high variability of raw web scrapes. LinkML serves as the validation bridge; it allows us to define schemas in non-technical YAML files that automatically generate Python dataclasses, ensuring that only high-quality data enters the graph. Neo4j is chosen as the operational database to leverage graph algorithms for analyzing complex relationships within procurement networks, while NeoDash provides a native, low-code solution for immediate data visualization.

Figure 3. Architecture Design

3.2. Mapping of Data Sources

The data collection procedure was designed to construct a holistic view of the Portuguese public procurement ecosystem. A key contribution of this project is the integration of public contract data (e.g., award details, scope, and entities) with information on the careers and activities of public and elected officials in Portugal. This unified dataset enables an investigation into potential favoritism or the use of political influence in public procurement, which may in turn reveal patterns indicative of collusion or conflicts of interest.

Table 1 summarizes the data sources used, detailing their relevance to the project and other key attributes. Table 2 provides an overview of the datasets that are stored in Neo4J and/or CouchDB, while indicating the data sources that populated each dataset and the possible relationships that can be identified. Finally, the pipelines that connect and integrate the data sources are described in [Section 3.3.](#), per dataset.

Table 1. Summary of data sources.

Sources	Data overview	Data type	Relevance	Accessibility
Portal BASE (base.gov.pt)	The source includes detailed records of public contracts executed across Portugal. It covers contracts signed since late 2008 and it is updated regularly.	Semi-structured.	Highly relevant to the scope of the project as it provides valuable information on potential competitive dynamics or relationships between companies.	Publicly available in open format or via unofficial APIs.
Anuário Financeiro dos Municípios Portugueses (occ.pt)	This yearly made report by the Ordem dos Contabilistas Certificados includes annual financial data about Portugal's public sector.	Structured.	Brings data on municipalities' ownership stakes in public entities, extent of each holding.	Publicly available in open format.
Portal Mais Transparência (transparencia.gov.pt)	This source includes detailed information on publicly financed projects in Portugal, as well as information on those who were awarded the financing.	Semi-structured.	Highly relevant to the scope as it provides information on potential competitive dynamics or relationships between companies.	Publicly available in open format.
Orbis (Now Moodys) (orbis.bvdinfo.com)	This database collects information on private companies, their financial activity, ownership and linkages.	Structured.	Highly relevant to the scope as it provides information regarding companies and owners, serving as a link between the several datasets.	Only available with an account.
ContratAR (app.parlamento.pt/ContratAR)	This page includes summary records of public contracts executed across Portugal awarded by the Portuguese Parliament (<i>Assembleia da República</i>), signed between 12/09/2022 and 30/05/2025. It also includes links that direct to the contract publications, with more in-depth information.	Semi-structured.	Highly relevant to the scope of the project as it provides valuable information on potential competitive dynamics or relationships between companies.	Publicly available in open format through the Portuguese Parliament platform.

Sources	Data overview	Data type	Relevance	Accessibility
Historical Portuguese Governments Archive on Constitutional Governments (historico.portugal.gov.pt)	Page centralizing public information regarding prior constitutional governments (I to XX), such as composition, nominations and governmental programs.	Unstructured.	Relevant to the scope of the project as it describes who is present in the Portuguese political/public sphere, possibly highlighting conflicts of interest.	Publicly available through the website.
Official Portuguese Government Portal of the Constitutional Government (portugal.gov.pt)	Official Portuguese government page, containing information on current and previous constitutional governments (since XXI). Includes marketing, composition, governmental programs, nominations, news, ministerial agendas, etc.	Unstructured.	Relevant to the scope of the project as it describes who is present in the Portuguese political/public sphere, possibly highlighting conflicts of interest.	Publicly available through the website.
Associação Nacional de Municípios Portugueses (ANMP) official list of Municipal Presidents (anmp.pt)	Official page for Portuguese municipalities, including news, composition, marketing, assessments, etc.	Unstructured.	Relevant to the scope of the project as it describes who is present in the Portuguese political/public sphere, possibly highlighting conflicts of interest.	Publicly available through the website.
Official Portuguese Elections Portal (eleicoes.mai.gov.pt)	Official page of candidates and results for Portuguese elections, as well as European Parliament elections. Covers all elections occurring between 2008 and 2025.	Unstructured.	Relevant to the scope of the project as it describes who is present in the Portuguese political/public sphere, possibly highlighting conflicts of interest.	Publicly available through the website.
Parliament Open Data (parlamento.pt)	Open data platform for the Portuguese Parliament, including information such as registers of interests, biographies, composition, parliamentary debates' transcriptions, etc, since 1974.	Semi-structured.	Highly relevant as it provides information on firms and other careers held by people with political influence in Portugal.	Publicly available in open format from the open data platform..
Moniz, N., & Campos, A. (2016). Relational Data on Members of Portuguese Governments (1976–2014). Data, 1(1), 1-8.	Dataset that covers information on people who were formal government members between 1976 and 2013. Information mostly	Structured.	Highly relevant as it provides information on firms and other careers held by people with political influence in Portugal.	Publicly available.

Sources	Data overview	Data type	Relevance	Accessibility
https://doi.org/10.3390/data1010001	regards connections to political/social occupations and/or private entities.			
Secretaria Geral do Ministério da Administração Interna (SGMAI) list of Election Dates (sg.mai.gov.pt)	Official page for <i>Secretaria-Geral do Ministério da Administração Interna</i> , including technical documentation, legislation and other administrative information.	Structured.	Provides complementary data to contextualize information from other sources.	Publicly available through the website.

Table 2. Datasets and relationship with data sources.

Dataset	Dataset overview	Relevant Data Sources	Relationships	Entities
Portal BASE	The dataset includes detailed records of public contracts executed across Portugal. It comprises 1,931,290 rows, 20 descriptive columns (plus 2 id columns) covering contracts signed between 2009 and 2024.	Portal BASE	Who contracted whom/who buys what from whom, who competes with whom etc.	Public, private companies and individuals.
Anuário Financeiro dos Municípios Portugueses	This yearly made report by the <i>Ordem dos Contabilistas Certificados</i> includes annual financial data about Portugal's public sector.	Anuário Financeiro dos Municípios Portugueses	Which public companies are owned by which municipality.	Public companies and municipalities.
Projetos (+Transparência)	The dataset includes detailed records on projects that were publicly financed under the scopes of PT2020, PT2030 and PRR programs.	Portal Mais Transparência	Per project, indicates the amount awarded by region, if applicable. Who was awarded which projects.	Publicly financed projects.
Beneficiários (+Transparência)	The dataset includes information on the entities that were awarded financing from projects under the scope of PT2020, PT2030 and PRR programs.	Portal Mais Transparência	Which financings were awarded to each beneficiary.	Entities (companies or people) who have been awarded a publicly financed project.
Projetos Pandemia (+Transparência)	This dataset includes records on projects that were publicly financed under the COVID-19 immediate recovery plan in Portugal.	Portal Mais Transparência	Per project, indicates the amount awarded by region, if applicable. Who was awarded which projects.	Publicly financed projects.
Beneficiários Pandemia (+Transparência)	The dataset includes information on the entities that were awarded financing from projects under the COVID-19 immediate recovery plan in Portugal.	Portal Mais Transparência	Which financings were awarded to each beneficiary.	Entities (companies or people) who have been awarded a publicly financed project.

Dataset	Dataset overview	Relevant Data Sources	Relationships	Entities
AR Contracts	The dataset includes detailed records of public contracts awarded by the Portuguese Parliament (<i>Assembleia da República</i>). It currently comprises 364 rows, 13 descriptive columns covering contracts signed between 12/09/2022 and 30/05/2025.	ContratAR	Who does the Portuguese Parliament contract, who competes with whom.	Public and private companies.
Municipal Presidents	This dataset contains information on all Portuguese municipal presidents, between 1976 and 2025, per term, totalizing 4121 rows. In some cases, it includes descriptive information such as the political party in representation during the mandate.	<p><i>Associação Nacional de Municípios Portugueses</i> (ANMP) official list of Municipal Presidents</p> <p>Official Portuguese Elections Portal</p> <p>Moniz, N., & Campos, A. (2016). Relational Data on Members of Portuguese Governments (1976–2014). <i>Data</i>, 1(1), 1-8.</p> <p>Secretaria-Geral do Ministério da Administração Interna (SGMAI) list of Election Dates</p>	Who carried out terms as a municipal president in Portugal, when, where, and in representation of which party.	Individuals.
Election Candidates	This dataset includes information on all candidates for any election between between 2009 and 2025, including local, legislative, regional and presidential portuguese elections, as well as European Parliament elections. It comprises 50553 rows and 10 columns. Whenever relevant, it includes descriptive information on the candidature such as electoral circle/municipality, result and party representation.	<p>Official Portuguese Elections Portal</p> <p>Secretaria-Geral do Ministério da Administração Interna (SGMAI) list of Election Dates</p>	Who participated in Portuguese elections and/or European Parliament elections and when, by which representation. Who won the elections.	Individuals.

Dataset	Dataset overview	Relevant Data Sources	Relationships	Entities
Government Members	This dataset contains information on individuals who have served throughout the different Portuguese constitutional governments, specifically ministers and secretaries. Data covers the I to XXV constitutional governments (1976-2025), comprising 1718 records and 3 descriptive columns, as well as time indicators (e.g., nomination date) and other identifiers.	<p>Official Portal of the Portuguese Constitutional Government</p> <p>Historical Archive on Portuguese Constitutional Governments</p> <p>Parliament Open Data</p> <p>Moniz, N., & Campos, A. (2016). Relational Data on Members of Portuguese Governments (1976–2014). <i>Data</i>, 1(1), 1-8.</p>	Who participated in the Portuguese government and when. Which roles were held in the Portuguese government and by who.	Individuals.
Government Offices' Members	This dataset contains information on people that were appointed to private office staff of government members, throughout the 19th to 24th Constitutional Governments, totalizing 5102 rows and 9 columns.	<p>Official Portal of the Portuguese Constitutional Government</p> <p>Historical Archive on Portuguese Constitutional Governments</p>	Who was nominated for government offices and when. Which roles were held in the offices and which ministerial they are subject to.	Individuals.
Parliament Members	The dataset includes information on all elected members of the Portuguese Parliament since the Constituent Assembly (<i>Assembleia Constituinte</i>), per legislature. It comprises 6053 rows and 13 descriptive columns, as well as an identifier.	Parliament Open Data	Who participated in the Portuguese Parliament, and when, by which representation.	Individuals.
Parliament/Government Members' Societies	Contains information from the registers of the Portuguese interests of members of Parliament between the 11th and 15th legislatures, inclusive, on social participation and/or links to companies/commercial entities. The dataset includes 172 rows and 8 columns.	Parliament Open Data	Who holds participation in a particular society.	Individuals.

Dataset	Dataset overview	Relevant Data Sources	Relationships	Entities
Parliament/Government Members' Other Careers	This dataset is based on the registers of interests of members of the Parliament between the 11th and 15th legislatures, inclusive, on positions that may prevent them from participating in certain parliamentary acts. Also includes information on miscellaneous careers from government members until 2014. Comprises 7084 rows and 18 columns.	Parliament Open Data Moniz, N., & Campos, A. (2016). Relational Data on Members of Portuguese Governments (1976–2014). <i>Data</i> , 1(1), 1-8.	Which careers and other activities parliament and government members are connected to.	Individuals.

3.3. Pipelines

Due to time constraints, a subset of the collected data was prioritized for integration into the final knowledge graph. However, all remaining data are documented in the preceding section to facilitate future research. The following subsections detail the primary pipeline applied to the core data sources used, from the Bronze level to the Gold-level and graph elements map.

3.3.1. Portal BASE

Bronze-level

BASE is Portugal’s official public-procurement portal. Data were collected via an unofficial API that mirrors information published on the [official site \(base.gov.pt\)](http://base.gov.pt); only publicly accessible content is included. The unit of analysis is the contract/procedure, providing record-level detail for each procurement procedure and resulting contract. The extract spans 2009–2024 and contains 1,931,289 records with 20 descriptive fields plus 2 identifier fields constituting the initial Bronze-level data for the pipeline.

Silver-level

The following transformations were performed to elevate the raw data to the Silver-level:

Table 4. Transformations Applied to Portal BASE data

Category	Transformation Applied
Standardization	Uniform formatting of CPVs, contract_type, and execution_location.
Data Imputation	Manual imputation of missing values for contracted and contracting_agency.
Temporal Filters	Removal of records with an execution_deadline exceeding 11,000 days (\approx 30 years).
Logical Consistency	Removal of records where the publication_date precedes the signing_date.
Financial Filters	Removal of records with an initial_price \leq 0 when the final_price was missing. direct to the contract publications, with more in-depth information.

Category	Transformation Applied
Feature Engineering	Calculation of the number of tenderers for each contract.

These steps excluded 6,243 records, yielding a modeling dataset of 1,925,046 contracts constituting the Silver-level data for the pipeline.

Gold-level

The Gold-level data was achieved by integrating external sources to add geographical and hierarchical depth to the Silver-level records.

- 1. Postal code & district:** Company tax identifiers (NIF) were used to query the public site nif.pt and retrieve postal codes. These postal codes were then mapped to districts, allowing the location of each company at the district level, since some postal codes were incomplete.
- 2. CPV metadata:** The available data in [cpv-eu](https://github.com/cpv-eu) GitHub repository was used to complete CPV hierarchy level, description, and parent code. This enabled reconstruction of the CPV tree for analysis.

Graph Nodes

The Gold-level data derived, is mapped to the nodes in Table 6:

Table 5. Nodes derived from Portal BASE data

Node Type	Description
Tender	The procurement process preceding a contract. Initiated, disputed and won by one or more entities.
Contract	Procurement agreement output of Tender and signed by one or more entities.
Entity	Organizations acting as either contracting authorities or economic operators (bidders).

Node Type	Description
Document	Official contract publications.
Location	Geographical classification (e.g., Districts or Municipalities).
CPV	Common Procurement Vocabulary codes representing the object of the contract.

Graph Edges

Table 6. Edges derived from Portal BASE data

Edge Type	Source Node	Target Node	Description
SIGNED_CONTRACT	Entity	Contract	Connects the winning contractor to the final agreement.
IS_PROCURING_ENTITY_FOR	Entity	Tender	Identifies the government body or agency issuing the tender.
IS_TENDERER_FOR	Entity	Tender	Links all participating bidders to a specific competition.
COMPETED_WITH	Entity	Entity	A peer-to-peer relationship between entities bidding on the same tender.
WON_TENDER	Entity	Entity	Specifically identifies the successful bidder of a procurement process.
AWARDS_CONTRACT	Tender	Contract	Links the procurement process to its resulting legal document.
HAS_DOCUMENT	Contract	Document	Connects contracts to their associated public records.
LOCATED_AT	Entity	Location	Maps an organization's headquarters or registered address.

Edge Type	Source Node	Target Node	Description
EXECUTED_AT_LOCATION	Contract	Location	Defines the geographic region where the contract's work is performed.
HAS_CPV_CLASSIFICATION	Contract	CPV	Categorizes the tender or contract within the CPV hierarchy.

Limitations

While a single tender can result in multiple contracts in practice, the available data often couples them into a **one-to-one relationship**. As this is the only comprehensive public data source available, the model adopts this structure. This limitation is acknowledged, but it does not compromise the overall integrity of the procurement analysis. Similarly, the **lack of recorded bid values** restricts the ability to analyze market competition in more detail.

3.3.2. Anuário Financeiro dos Municípios Portugueses (OCC)

Bronze-level

The annual reports from the **Ordem dos Contabilistas Certificados (OCC)** are published exclusively in PDF format, requiring the use of **Tabula** for structured table extraction. For this project, the 2021 report was processed to isolate the data in **Annex I (Anexo I)**. This extraction captured 479 records with 10 descriptive fields, primarily focusing on the ownership links and shareholding percentages between municipalities and their companies.

Silver-level

The following transformations were performed to elevate the raw data to the Silver-level:

Table 7. Transformations Applied to Portal OCC data

Category	Transformation Applied
Cleaning	Drop non-relevant columns
Remapping	Remap data so each document represent a entity, and have a field with municipality participation
NIF Mapping	Added NIF to entities to facilitate match with Portal BASE data

Gold-level

No additional data aggregation was needed to further enrich the dataset, as the extracted shareholding percentages and ownership links already provided the necessary depth. Consequently, this processed data serves as the Gold-level layer.

Graph Nodes

The Gold-level data derived, is mapped to the nodes in Table 8:

Table 8. Nodes derived from OCC data

Node Type	Description
Entity	Parent municipal entity and its subsidiary municipal companies,

Graph Edges

Table 9. Edges derived from OCC data

Edge Type	Source Node	Target Node	Description
ADMINISTRATED_BY	Location	Entity	Maps a geographic Location (Municipality) to the specific Entity (City Council/Câmara Municipal) responsible for its public administration and governance.
SHAREHOLDER_OF	Entity	Entity	Represents an equity ownership relationship between a parent municipal entity and its subsidiary municipal companies, as identified in the OCC reports.

3.3.3. Orbis

Bronze-level

A total of 114,197 unique valid NIFs were extracted from Portal BASE contracts and utilized as identifiers to query the Orbis database. This process yielded two primary datasets containing individual UCIs: (i) directors and managers, and (ii) shareholders.

Silver-level

The following transformations were performed to elevate the raw data to the Silver-level:

Table 10. Transformations Applied to Orbis data

Category	Transformation Applied
Renaming	Rename important columns to match in both datasets.
Name Normalization	Converted names to uppercase; removed common prefixes and all accentuation.
Group by UCI	Aggregated information at UCI, making each document a person with all associated metadata.

Gold-level

To reach the Gold-level, both datasets were cross-matched to create a comprehensive profile for each individual. This final layer identifies every person’s specific involvement in a company, classifying them as a shareholder, director, manager, or a combination of these roles.

Graph Nodes

The Gold-level data derived, is mapped to the nodes in Table 11 and edges in Table 12:

Table 11. Nodes derived from Orbis data

Node Type	Description
Person	A unique entity representing an individual, resolved via UCI to consolidate all leadership and ownership roles across multiple organizations.

Graph Edges

Table 12. Edges derived from Orbis data

Edge Type	Source Node	Target Node	Description
ASSOCIATED_WITH	Person	Entity	Connects individuals to organizations where they hold a formal position. The specific nature of the involvement (e.g., Director, Manager, or Shareholder) is stored as a role property on the edge, allowing for multi-role attribution.

Limitations

The main limitation was the high number of missing values for appointment and resignation dates, which made it impossible to calculate the duration of the roles which would enrich the temporal aspect of the graph.

3.3.4.Parliament/Government Members’ Societies & Other Careers

Bronze-level

Data on Parliament members’ registers of interests, as well as biographic registers extracted from the “Registo Biográfico” of the [Parliament Open Data](#) gave origin to two different but complementary dataset:

- i) The data coming from the “Sociedades” field (or variations depending on the legislature, such as fields with the prefix “rgs”) was isolated and structured into a dedicated file.
- ii) Information pertaining to “other careers,” “other activities,” and “social careers” was aggregated from the registers of interests into a separate dataset. This file was further enriched by appending relational data from the “[Relational Data on Members of Portuguese Governments](#)” specifically incorporating records where the “Organization” field referred to entities other than “Governo”, “Assembleia da República” or their variants.

Silver-level

The following transformations were performed to elevate the raw data to the Silver-level:

Table 13. Transformations Applied to Parliament members’ data

Category	Transformation Applied
Renaming	Rename important columns for better interpretability and consistency.

Category	Transformation Applied
Name Normalization	Converted names to uppercase; removed common prefixes and all accentuation.
'Governor' and 'Legislatura' Normalization	Converted roman numbers into integers, and ensured consistency.

Gold-level

Entities were enriched with NIPC identifiers to enable cross-matching with Portal BASE. Using the Google Search API, we applied a consensus-based validation method: only NIPCs that appeared consistently across various search queries were integrated into the final dataset. The few others that did not achieve consensus were manually searched and imputed.

Graph Nodes

The Gold-level data derived, is mapped to the nodes in Table 14 and edges in Table 15:

Table 14. Nodes derived from Parliament members' data

Node Type	Description
Person	A unique entity representing a politically exposed person (PEP) to be linked all historical and current roles across various political and corporate organizations.

Graph Edges

Table 15. Edges derived from Parliament members' data

Edge Type	Source Node	Target Node	Description
ASSOCIATED_WITH	Person	Entity	Defines a formal position held by a PEP within an organization. Specific titles or responsibilities are stored as attributes on the edge, enabling the representation of multiple, distinct roles for a single entity.

3.4. Graph Modelling and Characterization

Figure 4 presents the property graph model to which the structured data extracted from the multiple sources are mapped. This figure was generated by the LinkML library, which was employed to define the Application Profile, ensuring that the extracted data conforms to a standardized set of requirements and constraints.

Figure 4. Architecture Design.

3.5. Dashboard

To demonstrate the practical applications of the designed data pipeline, a dashboard was developed using NeoDash, a specialized visualization tool within the Neo4j ecosystem. The following sections provide a walkthrough of the various dashboard views, highlighting key functionalities and insights.

3.5.1. Data Summary

Figure 5 provides a dashboard overview of the database scale and structure, allowing users to familiarize themselves with the dataset through the following components:

- **Quantitative Metrics:** Real-time counters showing over 5.2 million nodes and 15.5 million relationships.

- **Entity Distribution:** A categorical breakdown of core classes, including Contracts, Tenders, and Entities.
- **Temporal Analysis:** A trend line illustrating the steady growth of procurement activity from 2009 to 2024.
- **Application Profile:** A visualization of the LinkML-generated graph schema, defining the semantic relationships that govern the knowledge graph.

Figure 5. Data Summary Dashboard View

3.5.2. Sector Explorer

Figure 6 illustrates the Sector Explorer view, which enables users to filter data by CPV codes and municipalities to analyze the sectoral and geographical landscapes of public procurement through the following components:

- **Market Dynamics:** Visualizations of market value evolution and aggregate total market value for the selected parameters.
- **Competitive Landscape:** An analysis of the top five market participants, including detailed metrics on market share and contract volume.
- **Procedural Distribution:** A breakdown of procurement methods to identify the prevalence of open, limited, or direct tenders.
- **Stakeholder Ecosystem:** A graph visualization of the top 10 contract stakeholders and the competitive network surrounding them.

Figure 6. CPV Sector Dashboard View

3.5.3. Entity Explorer

Figure 7 illustrates the Entity Explorer view, which allows users to perform targeted searches by VAT number to evaluate an entity's performance and competitive standing within the procurement landscape through the following components:

- **Performance Summary:** A high-level overview of the entity's participation metrics, including the total number of tenders entered, contracts won, and the overall win rate.
- **Competitive Intelligence:** A detailed table of the top 10 competitors ranked by frequency of interaction, featuring metrics such as competitor success rates and head-to-head win ratios. This component includes interactive functionality to generate a competition sub-graph, visualizing shared contracts and CPV codes.
- **Procedural Behavior:** A distribution analysis of procedure types used to assess the entity's participation patterns across open, limited, and direct tender categories.
- **Revenue Concentration:** A Pareto-style bar chart identifying the dominant CPV codes that constitute 80% of the entity's public contract revenue.

Figure 7. Entity Explorer Dashboard View

3.6. Conclusion

This project delivers an end-to-end architecture designed to bridge the gap between flat tabular data and the inherently relational nature of public procurement. By transforming Portal BASE records into a robust Relational Knowledge Graph—utilizing LinkML for schema modeling and graph databases for storage—we provide a more intuitive way to navigate complex contract networks. Whether helping businesses identify market opportunities or empowering investigators to detect suspicious patterns, this pipeline turns raw data into actionable intelligence.

The complete source code, schema definitions, and implementation details are available on [GitHub](#).

4. Predicting Market Evolution

4.1. Market Evolution as a Link Prediction Task using GNNs

Public procurement markets can be analysed as collections of individual contracts, evaluated independently in terms of prices, volumes, or procedural characteristics. While this perspective is useful for descriptive analyses, it provides only a partial view of how procurement markets operate and evolve over time. In practice, procurement outcomes emerge from repeated interactions among a relatively stable set of economic agents, whose relationships extend beyond a single contract (Sturm et al., 2025).

Accordingly, the following work conceptualizes the public procurement market as an evolving network of interacting firms. Firms participate in multiple procedures across time, frequently encountering the same competitors or partners. These repeated interactions give rise to relational structures, such as co-bidding patterns, recurrent market participation, and persistent supplier relationships. From this perspective, market evolution is partly driven by changes in the structure of relationships between firms. Viewing procurement markets as networks therefore allows market evolution to be understood as a dynamic view of firms' relationships.

Once procurement markets are conceptualized as evolving networks, market dynamics can be reframed as a prediction problem over network structure (Liben-Nowell & Kleinberg, 2003). Rather than being described solely in retrospective terms, market evolution can be formalized as anticipating how relationships between firms are likely to change over time.

In this framework, firms are represented as nodes and interactions between them as links. Market evolution is thus expressed through the emergence, persistence, or disappearance of links across successive time periods. Predicting whether a link between two firms will form or reoccur corresponds to the link prediction task in network science and machine learning, which aims to estimate the likelihood of future connections based on observed network structure and historical interactions (Lü & Zhou, 2010). Applied to procurement markets, link prediction enables the analysis to move beyond static descriptions of past behaviour and towards identifying latent relational tendencies that are not directly observable at the contract level.

Framing market evolution as a link prediction task requires modelling approaches capable of exploiting the relational structure of procurement markets and the firms present on them. Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) provide a natural framework for this context by explicitly operating on network-structured data. GNNs learn from both firm attributes and the structure of interactions, aggregating information from neighbouring nodes to capture how local and

broader network contexts influence the likelihood of future relationships. A key advantage of GNNs lies in their ability to model higher-order dependencies (Malla et al., 2025).

In public procurement, the focus is often on screening, prioritization, and early-warning mechanisms, where predictive performance and the identification of potentially relevant future interactions are central, suggesting that the use of GNNs is essential in forward-looking applications and is aligned with the development of risk-oriented analytical tools.

4.2. Data and Methods

The analysis relies on a dataset of public procurement contracts obtained from base.gov.pt. The original dataset comprises 1,931,290 contracts awarded between 2009 and 2024. Given the focus on competitive market dynamics, the analysis was restricted to contracts awarded through open tender procedures similar to other works done in public procurement (Lyra et al., 2021). Each contract links one or more firms to public sector entities, with firms identified using their Portuguese taxpayer identification number (NIF). The “contestants” field was used to extract valid participating firms and construct consistent firm identifiers.

Standard data cleaning procedures were applied to ensure quality and consistency. Contracts were excluded when NIFs did not comply with national standards or when execution deadlines were unrealistically long. Missing final prices were replaced with initial prices when no price variation was reported. After filtering and preprocessing, the resulting dataset includes 126,264 open tender contracts, involving 18,564 distinct firms. This cleaned dataset serves as the basis for the network construction and the subsequent analysis of market evolution.

To study competition from a relational perspective, firms were represented as nodes, and links between firms were derived from co-participation in the same open tender procedure, capturing direct competition between suppliers. Each contract involving multiple bidders was converted into pairwise firm-firm interactions. Repeated interactions across contracts and years were then aggregated, resulting in an undirected network of competitive relationships. Table 16 summarizes the main descriptive statistics of the resulting network.

The resulting network consists of 18,564 nodes and 488,182 unique firm-firm links. Most firms belong to a single giant connected component, which includes 18,218 firms (over 98% of all nodes) and 487,825 links, indicating a highly integrated procurement market in which most suppliers are indirectly connected through chains of competition.

Table 16. Open Tenders Network Descriptive Statistics

Statistic	
Nodes (Full Graph)	18564
Edges (Full Graph)	488182
Nodes (Giant Comp.)	18218
Edges (Giant Comp.)	487825
Average Degree (Giant Comp.)	54
Median Degree (Giant Comp.)	17
Max. Degree (Giant Comp.)	1682
Average Clustering Coef. (Giant Comp.)	0.69
Median Clustering Coef. (Giant Comp.)	0.73

Within the giant component, the average degree is approximately 54, while the median degree is 17, indicating the coexistence of many moderately connected firms alongside a smaller number of highly connected suppliers, which may reflect firms with broad market presence or frequent participation across procedures. The maximum degree of 1,682, highlights the presence of very central suppliers with broad competitive exposure. The network also displays a high level of clustering, with an average clustering coefficient of 0.69, suggesting that firms competing against similar rivals are also likely to compete among themselves. Together, these characteristics indicate a dense and highly structured competitive network, well suited for link prediction analysis.

To account for the temporal nature of procurement activity and to study market evolution in a forward-looking setting, firm-firm interactions were associated with the year of contract signing and split chronologically. The training period covers 2009-2022, the validation period corresponds to 2023, and the test period corresponds to 2024, following a standard temporal evaluation protocol (Rossi et al., 2020). This design ensures that models are trained exclusively on past interactions and evaluated on future market behaviour, reducing the risk of temporal leakage.

In addition to chronological splitting, evaluation focuses on a new-ties setting, where the objective is to predict firm-firm relationships that will appear for the first time in the future. Validation positive links correspond to interactions observed in 2023 that were absent during training, while test positives correspond to interactions first observed in 2024. By concentrating on newly forming relationships, this protocol directly targets structural changes in the competitive network.

Finally, firm-level characteristics were incorporated through node features derived from procurement activity during the training period. These features summarize firms' historical behaviour, including participation intensity, contract awards, price-related outcomes, exposure to competition, and duration of market activity, providing additional information to support predictive capabilities to Graph Neural Networks.

Model performance was assessed within a standard link prediction framework using Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) and Average Precision (AP), which evaluate the quality of link ranking under class imbalance and varying decision thresholds. In addition, Precision, Recall, and F1-score were considered to provide an interpretable assessment of classification performance at specific thresholds, reflecting the trade-off between identifying emerging relationships and limiting false positives. Together, these metrics offer complementary perspectives on predictive performance.

The analysis considers a set of representative models spanning three broad methodological families: structural heuristics, graph embedding methods, and graph representation learning models. This selection enables a systematic comparison between classical, interpretable approaches and more expressive learning-based models, while remaining aligned with the scale and structure of the procurement networks.

As a baseline, heuristic link prediction methods were employed. These methods rely exclusively on graph topology and assign scores to candidate links based on shared neighbourhood structure. In particular, Common Neighbors (CN), Adamic-Adar (AA), and Resource Allocation (RA) were used, each capturing different aspects of local overlap between firms' interaction neighbourhoods (Lü & Zhou, 2010). Despite their simplicity, such heuristics are widely used benchmarks and often provide strong performance in networks where repeated interactions and local clustering are prevalent.

To move beyond purely structural scoring rules, the analysis also includes a graph embedding approach, namely Deep Walk (Perozzi et al., 2014). This method learns low-dimensional vector representations of firms by simulating random walks over the network, such that firms with similar structural roles or neighbourhood contexts are embedded close to one another. Link

prediction is then performed by comparing the embeddings of firm pairs. DeepWalk provides an intermediate point between heuristic methods and neural models, capturing broader structural patterns while remaining computationally efficient.

The core of the analysis relies on graph representation learning models, which aim to learn expressive representations of nodes or node pairs by leveraging network structure and, when available, node-level information (Chikwendu et al., 2024). Within this family, three approaches were considered that rely on message-passing mechanisms and therefore fall within the GNN class. Graph Autoencoders (GAE) (Kipf et al., 2016) serves as a canonical encoder-decoder baseline for link prediction, learning node embeddings optimized directly for reconstructing observed interactions, while GraphSAGE (Hamilton et al., 2017) represents a GNN architecture that aggregates information from sampled neighbourhoods, making it suitable for large and evolving networks. Finally, BUDDY (Chamberlain et al., 2022) is a state-of-the-art link prediction model that leverages subgraph-sketches structural signals through extensive feature precomputation and lightweight learning components, enabling efficient and accurate prediction of new firm-firm relationships without explicit subgraph extraction used in SEAL (Zhang & Chen, 2018) that is extremely computational intensive.

Together, these models provide a diverse and complementary set of approaches for evaluating link prediction performance in procurement markets. By comparing heuristic, embedding-based, and graph representation learning methods under a common evaluation framework, the analysis aims to quantify the added value of increasingly expressive models for capturing the dynamics of market evolution. The following section presents and discusses the empirical results obtained for each model.

4.3. Results

All models were evaluated under the same temporal new-ties protocol, with performance measured using Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC), Average Precision (AP), Precision, Recall, and F1-score, as reported in Table 17. Together, these metrics allow for a comprehensive evaluation of how well different models identify emerging firm–firm relationships in public procurement markets.

At a high level, AUC and AP assess a model’s ability to rank true emerging relationships above non-links. In contrast, Precision, Recall, and F1-score reflect the trade-off between identifying potentially relevant interactions and limiting false positives. This distinction is particularly important in public procurement contexts, where analytical tools are typically used for screening and prioritization.

Table 17. Link prediction performance

Model	AUC	AP	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Common Neighbors	0.71	0.72	0.85	0.47	0.61
Adamic-Adar	0.71	0.72	0.88	0.46	0.61
Resource Allocation	0.71	0.72	0.88	0.46	0.61
Deep Walk	0.52	0.59	0.50	1	0.67
GAE	0.61	0.72	0.76	0.50	0.6
GraphSAGE	0.63	0.73	0.75	0.53	0.64
BUDDY	0.74	0.78	0.80	0.49	0.61

Structural heuristic methods such as Common Neighbors (CN), Adamic–Adar (AA), and Resource Allocation (RA) exhibit identical performance, achieving an AUC of 0.71 and an AP of 0.72. This confirms that local topological features, such as shared competitors, already capture a substantial portion of emerging relationships in procurement networks, consistent with the strong clustering and repeated interaction patterns observed in the network structure. These methods display high precision but lower recall, identifying that when a link is flagged it is often correct, but many emerging relationships remain undetected. As a result, their F1-score remains moderate.

The graph embedding method Deep Walk performs substantially worse in terms of ranking ability, with an AUC of 0.52 and an AP of 0.59. Although it achieves perfect recall, this comes at the cost of very low precision, resulting in a large number of false positives. From a procurement perspective, this behavior would translate into excessive alerts, limiting its usefulness for screening or prioritization despite a relatively high F1-score driven by over-prediction.

Graph representation learning models provide a more balanced performance profile. Graph Autoencoders (GAE) match heuristic performance in terms of AP, 0.72, while slightly improving recall, suggesting limited gains beyond local structure. GraphSAGE further improves both AUC and AP, achieving the highest recall among non-embedding models and indicating that message-passing mechanisms help generalize beyond immediate neighbourhood overlap.

The strongest results are obtained by BUDDY, which achieves the highest AUC and AP, 0.74 and 0.78, respectively. While maintaining precision comparable to heuristics, BUDDY substantially improves ranking quality, making it particularly effective at prioritizing the most relevant emerging firm-firm relationships. This performance highlights the value of incorporating richer structural signals when accurate prioritization is critical.

Overall, the results support modelling market evolution as a link prediction problem. The strong performance of heuristic methods confirms that procurement markets are highly structured, with repeated competition and dense local interactions. At the same time, representation learning models, particularly BUDDY, show that richer structural information can significantly improve the ranking of newly forming relationships.

From a public procurement perspective, Average Precision is especially relevant, as it reflects the ability to prioritize true emerging interactions among many potential non-links, allowing analysts to focus on a smaller and more relevant subset of cases. Taken together, the findings indicate that heuristics and representation learning models are complementary as simple heuristics offer fast and interpretable screening, while more expressive and computationally intensive models provide added value when accurate prioritization is critical for monitoring and risk assessment.

4.4. Conclusion

This work examined public procurement market evolution through a network-based and predictive perspective, framing changes in competitive structure as a link prediction problem over firm networks. By shifting the focus from isolated contracts to evolving patterns of firm-firm interactions, we were able to model the market evolution as a link prediction task and understand how different methodological families of methods perform on such conditions.

The results show that emerging relationships in procurement markets are not random, but instead follow structural regularities that can be learned from historical interaction patterns. Simple heuristic methods based on neighborhood overlap already capture a substantial portion of this structure, offering transparent and computationally efficient baselines. At the same time, more expressive representation learning models achieve higher ranking prediction performance, particularly when identifying newly forming relationships. In particular, the strong performance of BUDDY suggests that incorporating richer structural signals substantially enhances the ability to prioritize emerging interactions. This finding is especially relevant in public procurement contexts, where analytical tools are typically used to support screening, prioritization, and early-warning rather than real-time decision-making. In such settings, improvements in predictive accuracy may justify additional computational complexity.

Overall, this work demonstrates that modelling procurement markets as evolving networks and applying link prediction methods offers a meaningful and operational approach to analysing market evolution. Network-based learning provides a flexible foundation for supporting oversight and monitoring activities, enabling a shift from purely retrospective analyses toward more forward-looking assessments of competitive dynamics in public procurement systems.

5. Conclusions

This project brought together a highly qualified multidisciplinary research team comprising two faculty and two research fellows (also phd students at NOVA IMS), one senior investigator, and two master students. It relied exclusively on open-source data and focused on the Portuguese market, a specially relevant context for the application of network-based approaches, given the scale and structure of the available data.

The project made three core contributions aligned with its initial objectives: a comprehensive literature review establishing the theoretical and methodological foundations of network analysis to collusion detection, the development of a functional pipeline for data acquisition, storage and representation, and a case study illustrating the analytical and predictive potential of these methods in market analysis.

Collectively, these contributions provide a robust conceptual and empirical basis for future research on computational tools for market oversight, particularly within and for public administration, where the timely detection of irregularities and preservation of competitive integrity are paramount. The project further demonstrates the value of integrating open-source data with computational modelling techniques as a promising avenue for ongoing scientific inquiry.

Naturally, a project of this nature faced some limitations. Chief among these were time constraints, as the project's duration was shorter than initially envisioned; limited opportunities for coordination with public administration entities; and the inherent technical complexity of some tasks required iterative refinement. Nonetheless, all planned tasks were completed successfully and, in many respects, exceeded the expected outcomes.

Accordingly, and alongside this report, several outputs resulted from this project. An open software repository containing guidelines to implement a graph database pipeline for modelling public procurement markets and a dashboard, two Master's theses, and four scientific papers accepted (or in press) for publication in peer review journals or proceedings of international conferences. In addition, four more manuscripts are currently in submission stage, which we expect to have published throughout the year of 2026, and two additional master thesis as expected.

Looking ahead, the next step will be to implement and operationalize the developed pipeline within a real-world public sector setting. The prototype built during this project functions as a Minimum Viable Product, providing a solid foundation for subsequent deployment, refinement, and scaling in collaboration with institutional partners.

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Appendix A

Table 1. Overview of network-based studies

Study title	Study type	Model/Framework	Data	Data source	Year	Publication	Authors	Authors' Affiliations
Balancing competition and cooperation: Evidence from transatlantic airline markets	Empirical	Econometrics/statistical methods - Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) to estimate dynamic panel data with fixed effects	T100 International Segment dataset	US Department of Transportation, USA	2019	Transportation Research Part A-Policy and Practice	Bilotkach, V; Hüschelrath, K	Newcastle University, UK; Univ Appl Sci & Leibniz Association, Germany
Carrier collaboration with endogenous networks: Or, the limits of what carrier collaboration can achieve under antitrust immunity	Theoretical	Econometrics/ statistical methods (pricing model/demand functions)	N/A	N/A	2021	Journal of Air Transport Management	Czerny, AI; Jost, PJ; Lang, H; Mantin, B	Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Peoples R China; WHU - Otto Beisheim School of Management, Germany; University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg
Collusive networks in market-sharing agreements in the presence of an antitrust authority	Theoretical	Graph theory + Econometrics/Probability	N/A	N/A	2012	Journal of Economics & Management Strategy	Roldán, F	University of Navarra (IESE Business School), Spain
Complexity-minded antitrust	Conceptual	N/A	N/A	N/A	2023	Journal of Evolutionary Economics	Petit, N., Schrepel, T.	European University Institute, Italy; Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Netherlands
Cournot Competition in Networked Markets	Theoretical	Graph theory (bipartite graphs) + Econometrics	N/A	N/A	2019	Management Science	Bimpikis, K; Ehsani, S; Ilkiliç, R	Stanford University, USA; Universidad de Chile, Chile

Horizontal Shareholding and Network Theory	Theoretical	Network theory (input-output linkages)	N/A	N/A	2021	Yale Journal on Regulation	Romano, A		Yale University, USA
Institutional Investor Voting Behavior: A Network Theory Perspective	Theoretical	Network theory	N/A	N/A	2019	University of Illinois Law Review	Enriques, Romano, A	L;	University of Oxford, England & European Corporate Governance Institute, Belgium; Yale University, USA
Networks and compatibility - implications for antitrust	Theoretical	Network theory	N/A	N/A	1994	European Economic Review	Economides, White, Lj	N;	New York University, USA
Object-oriented Bayesian networks for a decision support system for antitrust enforcement	Empirical	Bayesian network/Probabilistic Expert System	6920 records from cases examined from 1991 to 2003	Italian Antitrust Authority, Italy	2013	Annals of Applied Statistics	Mortera, Vicard, Vergari, C	J; P;	Roma Tre University (Dipartimento Econ); University of Bologna, Italy
Price effects of airline consolidation: Evidence from a sample of transatlantic markets	Empirical	Econometrics/statistical methods - Pooled OLS estimation	Price data from the Data Bank 1A (DB1A - 10% sample of all tickets, where at least one flight segment is serviced by a US carrier)	US Department of Transportation, USA	2007	Empirical Economics	Bilotkach, V		University of California System, USA & University of California Irvine, USA
The role of networks in antitrust investigations	Theoretical	Network analysis + Econometrics (e.g. equilibrium analysis)	N/A	N/A	2019	Oxford Review of Economic Policy	Elliott, Galeotti, A.	M;	University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK; University of London, London, UK

Understanding specialist sharing: A mixed-method exploration in an increasingly price-competitive hospital market	Empirical	Social network analysis + interviews	Health insurance data	Dutch insurance companies' center for information and standardization in health care, The Netherlands	2016	Social Science & Medicine	Westra, D; Angeli, F; Jatautaite, E; Carree, M; Ruwaard, D	Maastricht University, Netherlands; Maastricht University School of Business and Economics, Netherlands
Using network theory to detect dominant cartel firms		Network analysis (centrality + cohesion measures, clustering)	Case file COMP/E-1/37.51 2-Vitamins	European Commission, Belgium	2016	Journal of Competition Law & Economics	Grau-Carles, P; Cuerdo-Mir, M	Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain